

Registration form for preparing the certification of a service in NFDI4Objects

Responsible for content: _____, Date: _____

(For definitions of terms, see document 01_Appendix_Terminology)

General information

Service provider	Link to partner website: ...
Service class (see definition)	<input type="checkbox"/> A: Technical service <input type="checkbox"/> B: Community-related service
Service category (see definition)	<input type="checkbox"/> Consortium service <input type="checkbox"/> Partner service
Type of service component (see definition)	<input type="checkbox"/> Web application <input type="checkbox"/> Tool/client <input type="checkbox"/> Database <input type="checkbox"/> Workflow/pipeline <input type="checkbox"/> Library/API <input type="checkbox"/> Support / Assistance / Consulting <input type="checkbox"/> Data curation <input type="checkbox"/> Training and education <input type="checkbox"/> Storage <input type="checkbox"/> Community management <input type="checkbox"/> Content creation
Service category according to N4O application (for internal purposes only) – assign new services separately	<input type="checkbox"/> Catalogue and Registry Services (CRoS) <input type="checkbox"/> Qualification Services (QuoS) <input type="checkbox"/> Support Services (SuS) <input type="checkbox"/> Authority File and Vocabulary Services (AVS) <input type="checkbox"/> Interoperability Services (IntS) <input type="checkbox"/> Data services (DaS) <input type="checkbox"/> Software Application Services (SAS) <input type="checkbox"/> Discovery services (DiS) <input type="checkbox"/> Storage Services (StoS) FAIRification services as <input type="checkbox"/> Data Management Services <input type="checkbox"/> Data Capturing Services <input type="checkbox"/> Data Enrichment Services <input type="checkbox"/> Data Discovery Services <input type="checkbox"/> Data Preservation Services

Brief description (max. 250 words)	Brief description (max. 250 words)
Development status	A: Technical service <input type="checkbox"/> Pre-Alpha First draft <input type="checkbox"/> Alpha First public release <input type="checkbox"/> Beta Final concept <input type="checkbox"/> Final release B: Community-related service <input type="checkbox"/> Initialised (published) <input type="checkbox"/> Consolidated
Version (only service class A)	Current version
Documentation	(Link to documentation or mission statement)
Licence/Terms of use	(Link to terms of use)
Link to the service	(Link to the service)

Organisational information

Funding / Business or organisational model / Ongoing organisational responsibility	Please provide/list further information on the financing of the service. <input type="checkbox"/> The service/staff is already in place and is supported by the service provider ("hosting institution") as a basic service task <input type="checkbox"/> Business/organisational model in planning/in progress <input type="checkbox"/> No information yet on the financial/personnel situation after the end of NFDI4Objects <i>(Necessary information on sustainability for the report to the DFG)</i>
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Mandatory for Category B "Community" services

Community involvement	How are the relevant and affected communities addressed? How can the communities contribute to the service?
Organisation of the community	Describe how the community-supported service is organised, especially if the service is not affiliated with an institution.
Quality assurance mechanisms	What procedures are used to ensure the quality of the results?
Operational stability	Please describe how reliable operation of the service is ensured

Support

Contact	Homepage or e-mail address of the contact person (contact person, NOT the website itself)
Helpdesk contact	
Support until	

Technical infrastructure

Mandatory for Category A "technical" services

Contingency plan	Please provide a description or link to a description of the emergency and recovery plan
Stability of operation	Please describe how reliable operation of the service is ensured

Documentation

Instructions and workflows/templates are provided	Is assistance provided to users in the form of best practice examples and/or workflow guidelines? Are general criteria in line with the FAIR principles communicated to data providers? If so, please include the links here
Communication strategies	How are users informed about news and current developments, e.g. via newsletters, mailing lists, websites, etc.?
Listed under:	<input type="checkbox"/> N4O Homepage: <input type="checkbox"/> DFG RIsources: <input type="checkbox"/> EOSC Marketplace: <input type="checkbox"/> FAIRsharing: <input type="checkbox"/> re3data: <input type="checkbox"/> Other: please specify and add link
Published information (DOI, etc.)	List of publications related to the service

Reports

Service category	
(Self-)evaluation	Are there any evaluation reports or similar documents that can be made available to the service monitoring team for certification purposes?
KPI monitoring	Do you use KPIs for the internal evaluation of your service, and if so, which ones?

Detailed description

Detailed description for internal use in evaluating the service profile. Please address at least the following aspects: target group, required skills, data type, formats, standards, application example/user journey.